

Analysis of the effect of various evidence tampering agents on DNA and gender predicting genes (*SOX9/FOXL2*) in human blood samples

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Abstract

DNA evidence plays a critical role in forensic science, providing precise identification in criminal investigations. However, intentional tampering using chemical agents such as acids, bleach, and fuel can degrade DNA and affect forensic conclusions. This study examines the impact of these chemical agents on the integrity of DNA and the detectability of gender-determining genes, *SOX9* and *FOXL2*, in human blood samples. Human blood samples (n=50) were analyzed under four experimental conditions. The same set of 50 samples were independently treated with bleach, acid (HCl) and fuel (petrol), while untreated aliquots of the same 50 samples served as controls and were stored under controlled conditions before DNA extraction using the salting-out method. DNA concentration and purity were assessed using a Nanodrop spectrophotometer, and polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was performed to amplify *SOX9* and *FOXL2* genes. Gel electrophoresis was used to determine the extent of DNA damage. Results indicate that acid treatment caused the most severe degradation, significantly reducing mean DNA concentration by ~94.9% with the lowest mean concentration (27.24ng/μl), and inhibiting PCR amplification. Bleach exposure led to oxidative DNA damage, resulting in inconsistent purity levels, while fuel (petrol) treatment caused moderate degradation, with partial loss of amplifiable DNA. The study highlights the vulnerability of forensic DNA to chemical tampering and the differential impact on specific genetic markers. The need for enhanced forensic methods to identify and retrieve damaged genetic material is highlighted by these findings. Alternative recovery techniques and the impact of additional chemical agents on the integrity of forensic DNA should be investigated in future studies.

Keywords: Chemical degradation, Evidence tampering, Forensic DNA, *FOXL2*, *SOX9*

1.0 Introduction

In the field of forensic science, proof in the form of DNA is considered one of the most essential pieces of evidence that is available [1]. This is because DNA is very distinct and can connect people and places to a crime scene with great precision, nevertheless, the issue of evidence tampering has been addressed more emphatically in recent years [2,3]. This is particularly so in the instance of solvents or other chemicals that can destroy or change the DNA structure, thereby affecting the results of a DNA test [4]. In some additional chemicals, for instance, the chemicals found in bleach and acids, as well as other chemical agents, are applied intentionally to blood samples to modify the DNA or protein

composition of the samples with the intent of hiding or eliminating critical data [5,6]. Forensic scientists face a major obstacle because not only does chemical tampering compromise the DNA integrity which reduces the efficiency of PCR amplification and genetic profiling, but also the structures of proteins that are significant for analysis are altered with the use of such compounds [6].

Knowing how such chemicals influence these specific genetic markers and proteins can be critical for the development of more appropriate forensic investigative approaches [7]. Special attention is given to gender-determining genes *SOX9* and *FOXL2*, with their manipulations

possibly leading to wrong conclusions; hence, very important research of their response to chemical exposure is being done [8]. Additionally, it will investigate the general degradation of proteins present in the blood, which might have implications for other forensic analyses [9,10]. Tampering with forensic evidence has been a growing concern in forensic analysis, notably through the use of chemicals [11]. This is coupled with the fact that a few of the chemical substances selectively destroy the genetic material or deplete it to a level that may not give accurate results when standard DNA tests are used [12,13]. In this case, the influence of such a variable would be relatively significant, especially at times when gender prediction or, most importantly, genetic determinants attached to that sample's origin have to be identified [14]. Furthermore, the potential tampering with proteins in the blood sample can interfere with forensic analysis that might be based on such proteins [15].

Consequently, the problem this research intends to resolve is the insufficient comprehension of how particular substances impact DNA, important genes such as *SOX9* and *FOXL2*, and blood proteins. Chemical and biological effects as such are important in coming up with forensic techniques that will be able to detect and perhaps recover altered genetic material [16]. This research is important for several reasons. First, it fills a gap in the existing forensic literature dealing with the impact of interference on DNA and protein structures. Even though the degradation of DNA caused by various environmental factors has been widely studied, there are few studies on the more specific chemical interference of particular genes, particularly *SOX9* and *FOXL2*. In this regard, the study helps forensic experts know what genes can be affected by tampering and the ways of minimizing those effects. Also, since *SOX9* and *FOXL2* have gender-dimorphic effects, the current study would enhance the effectiveness of assessing the gender of gender-biased forensic specimens. Such findings of the research might develop new forensic protocols and technologies that can detect tampering or repair of damaged DNA in forensic cases, thereby increasing the reliability of forensic evidence in court. In the long run, it could help in establishing forensic guidelines related to the handling of compromised biological evidence and thus increase the overall integrity of forensic investigations. Several limitations are obvious concerning this study. First, the scope of tested chemicals; cannot

include all possible substances used in tampering and will be biased toward commonly encountered agents such as bleach and acids [17]. Second, due to the difficult imitation of field conditions, almost real situations of tampering in the laboratory are hard to conduct because the extent and manner of applying a chemical may vary very much [18]. Other limitations would be that only two genes involved in the determination of one's gender were studied: *SOX9* and *FOXL2*. Not all genetic information could be tampered with. Lastly, while the research would try to study the effects on proteins, it may not also take into consideration the whole spectrum of types of proteins with different sensitivities to exposure to chemicals.

2.0 Materials and Methods

Sample Size: This present study included 50 samples from adult Nigerian male and female volunteers. The participants were selected based on their willingness to participate voluntarily.

Ethical Approval and Consent: This study was approved by the Health Research Ethics Committee of the University of Lagos, Nigeria (CMULHREC Number: CMUL/HREC/08/24/1670). All the processes of the study were explained to the participants. The participants consented verbally and they also signed a written consent form. Other basic information was collected from the participants. The study was carried out at the Chevron Molecular Biology Research Laboratory, University of Lagos Teaching Hospital.

Inclusion Criteria: The inclusion criteria for the study were carefully defined to ensure the reliability of the results. Participants were selected within the age range of 10 to 50 years to minimize variability in DNA and protein integrity associated with age. Only healthy individuals without chronic diseases, genetic disorders, or conditions that could affect DNA or protein stability were included. Those on long-term medication were excluded from participation. Additionally, individuals who had donated or participated in blood-related research within the last three months were not eligible, as such activities could influence blood cell counts or overall health status.

Exclusion Criteria: The study's exclusion criteria were established to ensure the accuracy and validity of the findings. Pregnant or breastfeeding

women were excluded due to hormonal changes that could impact gene expression and protein levels. Participants taking medications that influence the activity or expression of the *SOX9* or *FOXL2* genes were also excluded. Additionally, individuals who smoke or use recreational drugs were not eligible for participation, as these factors could interfere with the study's objectives.

Sample Collection: Blood samples were collected from 50 individuals. Four (4) Swab sticks were labelled according to the serial number assigned to each participant (1-50) and the treatment groups they are to be exposed to. The labelled swab sticks were dipped into their respective blood sample and covered to prevent any form of contamination. The swab sticks were then exposed to four experimental groups. Each swab stick was treated with one of three tampering chemicals (acid, bleach, or fuel), while one swab stick was left untreated to serve as a control. All samples were subsequently stored in a freezer for 24 hours before further analysis.

DNA Extraction: After 24 hours of exposure, the blood swab sticks were carefully cut into labeled Eppendorf tubes. Approximately 600 μL of saline solution was added to each tube containing the swab stick tips, mixed well using a brief vortex, followed by 6 μL of 20 mg/mL proteinase K. The samples were incubated at 60°C overnight and shaken at 40 rpm using an orbital shaker. After incubation, the samples were centrifuged for one minute at 5000 rpm, 150 μL of 4M NaCl, vortexed, and kept on ice for an hour after adding. The samples were centrifuged again at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes. 650ul of the supernatant was transferred to a new Eppendorf tube containing 650ul Isopropanol (not cold), and DNA was precipitated at room temperature for approximately 90 mins. Samples were vortexed briefly and centrifuged for 10 minutes. The supernatant was carefully discarded without disturbing the pellet. Approximately 500 μL of 70% ethanol was added, and the samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatant was carefully discarded, ensuring the pellet was not dislodged. The tubes were air-dried until all ethanol had evaporated. Finally, 50 μL of injection water was added to each tube and sample pellet.

DNA quantity and quality Nanodrop Spectrophotometer: The extracted DNA samples were examined using a Nanodrop 1000

spectrophotometer to determine their quality and quantity.

Gradient PCR and Determination of Optimal Annealing Temperature: 240 μL of injection water (10 μL each reaction), 96 μL of Mastermix (4 μL per reaction), 12 μL of forward primer (0.5 μL per reaction), and 12 μL of reverse primer (0.5 μL per reaction) were used to prepare the reaction cocktail for 24 reactions. Each PCR tube contained 5 μL of the DNA sample and a final volume of 15 μL for each reaction. Before being put into the thermocycler, the tubes were inverted and centrifuged for 30 seconds to ensure they were properly mixed. The ideal annealing temperatures for the genes *SOX9* and *FOXL2* were ascertained by gradient PCR using the following gradient: 66 °C, 64.8 °C, 62.7 °C, 59.7 °C, 56.1 °C, 53.1 °C, 51.1 °C, and 50.0 °C. 1g of agarose powder was dissolved in 100 ml of 0.5x TBE buffer, heated for 2 minutes in a microwave, and combined with 5 μL of ethidium bromide after PCR. The electrophoresis tank with 0.5x TBE buffer was filled with the gel. 5 μL of the PCR product were added to each well, and the electrophoresis was run for 30 minutes at 100 V and 300 A. The gel was removed after electrophoresis, and the ideal annealing temperature was assessed using an AlphaImager.

PCR Amplification of *SOX9* and *FOXL2* genes: For every sample, 15 μL of PCR cocktail solution was made in an Eppendorf tube. This solution included 10 μL of injection water, 4 μL of master mix, 0.5 μL of forward primer, and 0.5 μL of reverse primer. After pipetting this mixture into separate PCR tubes, 5 μL of isolated DNA was added. The samples were placed into the thermocycler after being carefully mixed. The thermocycler was set up with the following parameters: 30 cycles of an initial denaturation stage at 95 °C, annealing at 54 °C, and extension at 72 °C. The samples were subjected to an indefinite hold at 4 °C.

Restriction Enzyme Digestion: The cocktail solution, which included 0.9 μL of injection water, 1.0 μL of buffer, and 0.1 μL of the restriction enzyme EcoRI, was made in an Eppendorf tube, spun down, and then pipetted into each PCR tube in an amount of about 2 μL . Following that, the tubes holding the 2 μL cocktail solution were gently mixed with 8 μL of PCR products included. After preheating the water bath to 37 °C, the tubes were put in a styrofoam holder and incubated for two hours.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for DNA concentration

	Untreated	Bleach	Fuel	Acid
Number of values	50	50	50	50
Minimum	-295.7	-1400	0.000	-1.382
Maximum	12726	735.3	2468	275.9
Range	13022	2135	2468	277.2
Mean	537.6	173.8	157.0	27.24
Std. Deviation	1808	315.1	355.3	44.09

Figure 1: Comparison of Mean DNA concentration across Treatments.

A one-way ANOVA revealed a significant difference among the mean DNA concentrations across the four groups ($F = 2.746$, $p = 0.0442$). Post-hoc Tukey's multiple comparison test indicated that the DNA concentration of untreated samples was significantly higher than that of acid-treated samples ($p = 0.0347$). However, comparisons between untreated vs. bleach-treated ($p = 0.2127$) and untreated vs. fuel-treated ($p = 0.1787$) samples did not yield statistically significant differences. Bartlett's test for homogeneity of variances showed significant differences among the treatment groups ($p < 0.0001$).

Table 3: ANOVA for DNA concentration

ANOVA summary	
F	2.746
P value	0.0442
P value summary	*
Significant diff. among means ($P < 0.05$)?	Yes
R squared	0.04034
Brown-Forsythe test	
F (DFn, DFd)	2.865 (3, 196)
P value	0.0379
P value summary	*
Are SDs significantly different ($P < 0.05$)?	Yes
Bartlett's test	
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)	432.4
P value	<0.0001

Table 4: Post-hoc Tukey's multiple comparison test

Tukey's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	
Untreated vs. Bleach	363.8	-120.8 to 848.3	No	ns	0.2127	A-B
Untreated vs. Fuel	380.6	-104.0 to 865.2	No	ns	0.1787	A-C
Untreated vs. Acid	510.4	25.77 to 994.9	Yes	*	0.0347	A-D
Bleach vs. Fuel	16.83	-467.7 to 501.4	No	ns	0.9997	B-C
Bleach vs. Acid	146.6	-338.0 to 631.2	No	ns	0.8617	B-D
Fuel vs. Acid	129.8	-354.8 to 614.3	No	ns	0.8994	C-D

DNA purity Analysis: The purity of DNA samples was assessed using spectrophotometric measurements at A260/A280 ratios. The untreated samples exhibited relatively stable DNA purity levels, with values ranging from 0.76 to 5.55. The mean purity was 1.132 ± 0.6516 , with the highest recorded purity at 5.55 and the lowest at 0.76. A significant increase in DNA purity variability was observed in the bleach-treated samples, where values ranged widely from 0.99 to 59.69. The mean purity in this group was 2.402 ± 8.268 , with a sharp increase in maximum purity to 59.69, while the lowest recorded value remained at 0.99. The fuel-treated samples showed a decrease in DNA purity, with values ranging from -6.139 to 1.831. The mean purity was 0.7842 ± 1.053 , indicating a decline in DNA quality compared to the untreated group. The lowest recorded purity was -6.139, whereas the highest was 1.831. For the acid-treated samples, DNA purity values ranged from -2.235 to 4.044, with a mean of 1.123 ± 0.7362 . The lowest recorded purity was -2.235, while the highest reached 4.044, illustrating a reduction in DNA quality when compared to

untreated samples. Figure 2 showed the comparison of mean DNA purity across treatments.

Figure 2: Comparison of Mean DNA purity across Treatments.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics for DNA purity

	Untreated	Bleach	Fuel	Acid
Number of values	50	50	50	50
Minimum	0.7600	0.9900	-6.139	-2.235
Maximum	5.550	59.69	1.831	4.044
Range	4.790	58.70	7.970	6.279
Mean	1.132	2.402	0.7842	1.123
Std. Deviation	0.6516	8.268	1.053	0.7362

ANOVA results for DNA purity showed no significant difference among the mean values across the four groups ($F = 1.443$, $p = 0.2315$). However, Bartlett's test indicated significant differences in standard deviations ($p < 0.0001$).

Post-hoc Dunn's multiple comparison test showed significant differences between untreated vs. bleach-treated samples ($p < 0.0001$), bleach vs. fuel ($p < 0.0001$), bleach vs. acid ($p = 0.0003$), and fuel vs. acid ($p = 0.0008$), indicating that

bleach had the most variable impact on DNA purity.

Table 6: ANOVA for DNA purity

ANOVA Summary	
F	1.443
P value	0.2315
P value summary	ns
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	No
R squared	0.02161
Brown-Forsythe test	
F (DFn, DFd)	0.6840 (3, 196)
P value	0.5628
P value summary	ns
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
Bartlett's test	
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)	418.6
P value	<0.0001

Table 7: Post-hoc Dunn's multiple comparison test for DNA purity

Tukey's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	
Untreated vs. Bleach	-1.269	-3.444 to 0.9053	No	ns	0.4320	A-B
Untreated vs. Fuel	0.3480	-1.827 to 2.523	No	ns	0.9759	A-C
Untreated vs. Acid	0.009588	-2.165 to 2.184	No	ns	>0.9999	A-D
Bleach vs. Fuel	1.617	-0.5573 to 3.792	No	ns	0.2201	B-C
Bleach vs. Acid	1.279	-0.8958 to 3.454	No	ns	0.4252	B-D
Fuel vs. Acid	-0.3384	-2.513 to 1.836	No	ns	0.9778	C-D

FOXL2 Gene Amplification Analysis: The amplification results of the *FOXL2* gene for samples treated with acid, bleach, fuel, and untreated controls were analyzed using gel electrophoresis as shown in plates 1-7. The presence or absence of a distinct band was recorded for each sample. The gel electrophoresis results for the amplification of the *FOXL2* gene in acid-treated samples showed that among the 49 samples analyzed, 21 showed a distinct 100 bp band. Specifically, amplification was observed in samples 2A, 3A, 5A, 6A, 9A, 10A, 14A, 15A, 16A, 17A, 20A, 21A, 23A, 24A, 29A, 30A, 31A, 32A, 41A, 45A, and 49A. The remaining samples, including 4A, 7A, 8A, 11A, 13A, 18A, 19A, 22A, 26A, 28A, 33A, 40A, 42A, 44A, 46A, and 48A, did not display any visible bands on the gel. In bleach-treated samples, gel electrophoresis results demonstrated the presence of a 100 bp band in 37 out of 50 samples analyzed. Bands were observed in samples 1B, 2B, 4B, 5B, 6B, 7B, 8B, 9B, 10B, 11B, 12B, 13B, 14B, 15B, 16B, 18B, 19B, 21B,

23B, 24B, 25B, 26B, 27B, 28B, 29B, 33B, 34B, 43B, and 46B. However, the remaining samples, including 20B, 22B, 30B, 32B, 35B, 41B, 44B, 45B, and 47B and 50B, did not show any visible bands. For fuel-treated samples, 49 samples were subjected to gel electrophoresis. Among these, 35 samples displayed the presence of a 100 bp band. Of these bands were observed in samples 1F, 6F, 8F, 12F, 14F, 16F, 17F, 19F, 21F, 23F, 26F, 27F, 28F, 29F, 30F, 31F, 34F, 35F, 37F, 39F, 41F and 46F. The remaining samples, including 7F, 13F, 15F, 18F, 20F, 22F, 32F, 40F, 47F and 49F, did not exhibit any visible bands. In untreated samples, gel electrophoresis results revealed that 34 out of the 50 samples analyzed displayed a 100 bp band. Amplification was observed in samples 1U, 3U, 5U, 7U, 9U, 11U, 13U, 16U, 18U, 19U, 20U, 22U, 27U, 28U, 29U, 31U, 34U, 39U, and 41U. The remaining samples, including 4U, 6U, 10U, 12U, 23U, 26U, 30U, 32U, 33U, 35U, 38U, 42U and 48U, showed no visible bands.

SOX9 Gene Amplification Analysis: The gel electrophoresis results for the *SOX9* gene amplification in acid-treated samples showed that out of 49 samples analyzed, distinct bands were observed in several samples. Specifically, samples 1A, 2A to 5A, 19A to 21A, 23A to 27A, 29A to 30A, 35A, 37A to 38A, 40A, 41A, 44A to 47A, and 49A displayed 100 bp bands. However, no bands were observed in samples 6A to 18A, 22A, 28A, 31A to 34A, 36A, 39A, 42A to 43A, and 50A. For bleach-treated samples, 100 bp bands were detected in samples 1B to 5B, 7B to 8B, 9B, 11B to 15B, 17B to 18B, 23B, 25B to 26B, 27B, 29B, 30B, 32B to 33B, 34B, 38B to 39B, 40B to 41B, 42B to 43B, 45B to 46B, and 49B. No bands were visible in samples 6B, 10B, 16B, 19B to 22B, 24B, 28B, 31B, 35B to 37B, 44B, 47B to 48B, and 50B. In the fuel-treated group, bands were observed in samples 1F, 2F, 3F to 5F, 8F to 12F, 15F, 19F, 21F, 24F to 26F, 28F to 30F, 35F, 38F, 42F, 44F, and 46F. The remaining samples, including 6F to 7F, 13F to 14F, 16F to 18F, 20F, 22F to 23F, 27F, 31F to 34F, 36F to 37F, 39F to 41F, 43F, 45F, and 47F to 50F, displayed no visible bands. For untreated samples, bands were observed in samples 1U to 3U, 5U to 6U, 7U to 8U, 11U to 12U, 14U to 15U, 16U to 18U, 19U to 24U, 27U to 29U, 32U to 34U, 36U to 39U, 40U to 41U, 42U to 43U, 44U, and 46U to 50U. No bands were seen in samples 4U, 9U, 30U to 31U, 35U, and 45U. The band visibility for the *SOX9* gene was illustrated in plate 8-13.

Plate 1: Gel Electrophoretic band of *FOXL2* gene in sample 2A-40A.

Plate 2: Gel Electrophoretic band of *FOXL2* gene in sample 41A-49A.

Plate 3: Gel Electrophoretic band of *FOXL2* gene in sample 1B-40B.

Plate 4: Gel Electrophoretic band of *FOXL2* gene in sample 41B-50B and 1F-33F.

Plate 5: Gel Electrophoretic band of *FOXL2* gene in sample 34F-49F.

Plate 8: Gel Electrophoretic band of *SOX9* gene in sample 1A-36A.

Plate 6: Gel Electrophoretic band of *FOXL2* gene in sample 1U-33U.

Plate 9: Gel Electrophoretic band of *SOX9* gene in sample 37A-50A and 1B-

Plate 7: Gel Electrophoretic band of *FOXL2* gene in sample 34U-49U.

Plate 10: Gel Electrophoretic band of *SOX9* gene in sample 22B-50B and 1F-8F.

Plate 11: Gel Electrophoretic band of *SOX9* gene in sample 9F-46F.

Plate 12: Gel Electrophoretic band of *SOX9* gene in sample 46F-50F and 1U-36U.

Plate 13: Gel Electrophoretic band of *SOX9* gene in sample 37U-50U.

4.0 Discussion

Forensic science heavily relies on DNA evidence due to its high specificity in linking individuals to crime scenes, however, forensic investigations face challenges related to evidence tampering, particularly with chemicals that degrade or alter DNA structure [19,3].

The results from this study demonstrate that evidence-tampering agents, such as acid, bleach, and fuel, significantly impact DNA integrity. Acid treatment resulted in the most severe degradation, with significantly reduced DNA concentrations. This aligns with the report by Lee *et al.* [20], who demonstrated that acids hydrolyze phosphodiester bonds in DNA, leading to rapid strand breakage and depurination. Additionally, Özay and McCalla [21], reported that strong acids disrupt DNA secondary structures, making subsequent amplification difficult. The study supports these observations, as acid-treated samples exhibited minimal amplifiable DNA, indicating substantial nucleic acid breakdown. Unlike Özay and McCalla [21], who focused on controlled acidic hydrolysis, this study incorporates forensic application by simulating real-world tampering conditions. Bleach (sodium hypochlorite) is widely recognized for its ability to degrade nucleic acids, the bleach-treated samples also demonstrated substantial DNA degradation, corroborating findings from Martin [22], who demonstrated that bleach induces oxidative DNA damage by generating reactive oxygen species (ROS). These ROS interact with guanine bases, leading to mutations and fragmentation [23]. Compared to this study results, Edler *et al.* [24] reported similar trends, but with less severe degradation, likely due to differences in bleach concentration and exposure duration. Fuel-treated samples illustrated a moderate reduction in DNA concentration, supporting Rajput [15], who found that petroleum-based solvents cause lipid peroxidation, leading to DNA damage. While this study suggests that fuel primarily affects DNA solubility rather than direct fragmentation, previous research [25] indicates that prolonged fuel exposure can denature nucleic acids through solvent-mediated phase separation.

Spectrophotometric analysis revealed significant variability in DNA purity among treatment groups, with bleach-treated samples exhibiting the highest fluctuations. Singh *et al.* [26] attributed this to oxidative modification of DNA bases, leading to absorbance inconsistencies at 260/280

nm. The study corroborates these findings, as bleach-treated DNA exhibited a wide range of purity values, suggesting incomplete degradation and formation of modified nucleotides. Acid-treated samples exhibited relatively stable, but low, DNA purity values. Tevonyan *et al.* [27] suggested that acid-induced depurination leads to a consistent reduction in absorbance, which aligns with these findings. However, their study reported greater variability due to differences in DNA sequence susceptibility to acid hydrolysis. Fuel-treated samples exhibited the lowest purity, likely due to co-extraction of hydrocarbons that interfere with absorbance readings [8]. This contrasts with these findings, where DNA purity in fuel-treated samples remained relatively consistent, albeit lower than in untreated controls.

The impact of chemical exposure on the amplification of gender-predicting genes (*SOX9* and *FOXL2*) was evident in the gel electrophoresis results. Acid-treated samples exhibited the most severe loss of amplifiable DNA. Zhang [28] found that acid-induced DNA degradation leads to the loss of PCR efficiency, consistent with these findings. The absence of visible bands in acid-treated samples further supports the idea that acidic hydrolysis disrupts primer binding and polymerase activity, making it difficult to amplify genes crucial for gender determination. Bleach-treated samples retained a higher rate of successful amplification compared to acid-treated samples. This suggested that bleach-induced oxidation causes lesions that hinder but do not entirely prevent PCR. However, these results indicate that bleach exposure can differentially affect specific genetic regions, with *SOX9* showing slightly higher amplification rates than *FOXL2*. This could be due to differences in the GC content and sequence composition of the two genes, a phenomenon also observed by Zhao *et al.* [29]. Fuel-treated samples exhibited intermediate effects, with partial loss of amplifiable DNA. Chatterjee *et al.* [30] suggested that fuel components, such as benzene and toluene, can intercalate between DNA bases, leading to polymerase stalling. These results partially support this hypothesis, as some samples still produced bands, indicating that DNA damage was not entirely inhibitory. However, *FOXL2* amplification was more affected than *SOX9*, suggesting that solvent-based interference might influence gene-specific amplification differently. These findings align with a growing body of literature emphasizing the vulnerability of forensic DNA to chemical tampering. Prior

reports, including those by Özyay and McCalla, [21] and Zhang [12] have documented the destructive effects of strong acids on DNA integrity. Similarly, studies by Martin [22] and Edler *et al.* [24] have reinforced the notion that oxidizing agents like bleach can selectively degrade DNA, compromising forensic analysis.

However, this study extends this discourse by evaluating the differential impact of tampering agents on sex-determining genes (*SOX9* and *FOXL2*). Unlike previous studies that primarily assessed general DNA degradation, these results provide information into how these chemicals specifically affect forensic markers critical for gender determination. The selective damage to *FOXL2* observed in fuel-treated samples suggests that hydrocarbon contamination may introduce sequence-specific inhibitory effects, a concept that has not been extensively explored in forensic research. This has significant forensic implications, particularly in cases where accurate identification of biological sex is necessary for criminal investigations. If key genetic markers such as *SOX9* and *FOXL2* are selectively degraded, forensic experts may need to adjust their methodologies, possibly incorporating next-generation sequencing techniques or alternative genetic markers that are more resistant to chemical interference.

A wider variety of chemical tampering agents and their effects on nuclear and mitochondrial DNA should be investigated in future studies. Forensic analysis of compromised material should also be improved by looking into alternate DNA recovery methods like next-generation sequencing and specific PCR enhancement approaches. Proteomic analysis combined with DNA research may also provide a supplementary understanding of the mechanisms underlying evidence deterioration and preservation. The question of whether distinct sequence compositions affect a gene's vulnerability to chemical degradation is an important area for additional research. Obtaining knowledge about the molecular processes underlying the selective degradation of *SOX9* and *FOXL2* may enhance forensic procedures and result in more accurate DNA-based gender determination in damaged samples.

5.0 Conclusion

This study emphasizes how chemical tampering significantly affects DNA integrity and the amplification of forensic markers *FOXL2* and

SOX9. Acid caused the most damage to DNA, while fuel, bleach, and acid all showed varied degrees of DNA degradation. The results, which evaluate gene-specific susceptibility, advance forensic understanding while supporting earlier studies on DNA degradation pathways. The differential effects observed in SOX9 and FOXL2 amplification emphasize the need for forensic scientists to consider sequence-specific degradation when analyzing compromised samples. According to these findings, traditional DNA analysis might not be enough in situations involving chemical tampering, requiring the use of different strategies including next-generation sequencing and sophisticated PCR-enhancing techniques. The study emphasizes how crucial it is to create forensic procedures that consider chemical influence to guarantee the validity of genetic evidence in court.

Declarations

This manuscript titled “Analysis of the effect of various evidence tampering agents on DNA & gender predicting genes (*SOX9/FOXL2*) in human blood samples” is being submitted to your journal and is not currently under consideration elsewhere.

The co-authors are fully aware of this submission. This research work was personally sponsored by the authors. There is therefore no conflict of interest with any organization or individual on the work. Considering the importance of the work, publishing it in a reputable Journal like yours will be of immense significance and will contribute to knowledge in the scientific world.

Ethics approval and consent to participate: The study was approved ethically by the Health Research Ethics Committee (HREC) of the University of Lagos College of Medicine (Ref No: CMUL/HREC/08/24/1670). According to CMULHREC standards regarding research involving human or animal participants, the project was evaluated and found to comply with procedure and safety criteria.

Consent to publication: Not applicable.

Availability of Data and Materials: The data sets used and/or analyzed during this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Code Availability: Not applicable

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Funding: None

Authors’ contributions: All the Authors participated in the conceptualization and design of the research, carried out Ribonucleic acid (RNA) extraction, Complementary DNA (cDNA) synthesis and quantitative PCR (qPCR). Akpan MENEREBOBONG wrote the initial manuscript draft. Tochukwu Frank EGWUATU performed the statistical analysis. Onyekachi Ogbonnaya IROANYA coordinated and supervised the research, and carried out the final editing of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Data Availability Statement: The authors declare that data for this research are available upon request from the corresponding author

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